

Synthesis and Fungitoxicity of Nitrophenyl Sulphides and Sulphones

(Miss) PREM DUREJA & S. P. GUPTA

Department of Chemistry, D. N. College, Meerut.

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RECENTLY several nitrophenyl sulphides and Sulphones were found to possess excellent fungicidal activity^{1,2}. As a part of systematic search for potentially biological active compound, several polynitrophenyl sulphides and sulphones containing halo, nitro and methyl groups have been synthesised.

The polynitrophenyl sulphides have been prepared by the condensation of halogeno-nitrobenzenes with-p-chlorothiophenol in ethanolic solution. The sulphides on oxidation with a mixture of potassium permanganate and acetic acid yield the corresponding sulphones.

The fungicidal activity of these polynitrophenyl sulphides and sulphones was determined and the results are summarised in Tables 1 and 2.

Experimental

1. *p*-chlorophenyl-halogenonitrophenyl-sulphide : A solution of *p*-chlorothiophenol (0.01M) in alcohol (20.0 ml) and Caustic Soda (.01 M) in water (4.0 ml) was treated with a solution of halogenonitrobenzene (.01 M) in alcohol (15-20 ml). The mixture was refluxed on a water bath for about an hour and filtered. The hot filtrate on cooling gave crystals of the sulphides in almost quantitative yields which were further purified by crystallisation from alcohol. The analytical data and fungitoxicity are given in Table 1.

2. *p*-chlorophenyl halogeno-nitrophenyl sulphones : A solution of aryl polynitro-phenyl sulphides (.01 mol) in glacial acetic acid (sufficient to dissolve) was treated with potassium permanganate (40% excess of the calculated amount) dissolved in 20 times of its weight of water with stirring and kept for half an hour at room temperature. Excess potassium permanganate was removed by treatment with sulphurous acid. The sulphone was precipitated by adding ice to the mixture, and crystallised from alcohol. Compounds prepared are reported in Table 2.

TABLE 1—*p*-CHLOROPHENYL-HALOGENONITROPHENYL SULPHIDE

Srl. No.	R	Cl M.P. °C	Yield %	S-R Mol. Formula	% Sulphur		%Nitrogen		%Germination at 10 p.p.m.	
					Found	Requ.	Found	Requ.	AT	AN
1.	2,4-DNP	88	80	C ₁₂ H ₇ ClN ₂ O ₄ S	10.33	10.32	9.50	9.17	20	26
2.	2,6-DNP	125	75	C ₁₂ H ₇ ClN ₂ O ₄ S	10.19	10.32	9.62	9.17	18	24
3.	2,4,6-TNP	104	82	C ₁₂ H ₆ ClN ₃ O ₆ S	8.48	8.31	11.73	11.83	15	10
4.	2-Chloro-4,6-DNP	132	62	C ₁₂ H ₆ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₄ S	10.18	10.22	8.00	8.11	10	9
5.	2-Bromo-4,6-DNP	144	70	C ₁₂ H ₆ ClBrN ₂ O ₄ S	8.10	8.24	7.25	7.19	12	14
6.	3-Chloro-4,6-DNP	128	85	C ₁₂ H ₆ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₄ S	10.32	10.22	8.12	8.11	38	40
7.	4-Chloro-2,6-DNP	93	75	C ₁₂ H ₆ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₄ S	10.10	10.22	8.25	8.11	15	13
8.	2-methyl-4,6-DNP	142	80	C ₁₃ H ₉ ClN ₂ O ₄ S	9.73	9.87	8.75	8.91	45	50
9.	3-methyl-4,6-DNP	107	85	C ₁₃ H ₉ ClN ₂ O ₄ S	9.50	9.87	8.81	8.91	42	44
10.	4-methyl-2,6-DNP	98	90	C ₁₃ H ₉ ClN ₂ O ₄ S	9.70	9.87	8.85	8.91	30	32
11.	3-methyl-2,4,6-TNP	165	82	C ₁₃ H ₈ ClN ₃ O ₆ S	8.73	8.69	11.65	11.35	28	25
12.	2,3-Dichloro-4,6-DNP	115	70	C ₁₂ H ₅ Cl ₃ N ₂ O ₄ S	8.32	8.44	7.28	7.39	20	22
13.	2-Chloro-3-Bromo-4,6-DNP	110	75	C ₁₂ H ₅ Cl ₂ BrN ₂ O ₄ S	7.42	7.56	6.68	6.61	22	25
14.	2-Chloro-5-methyl-4,6-DNP	101	80	C ₁₃ H ₈ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₄ S	8.70	8.91	7.70	7.77	24	26
15.	2-Bromo-5-methyl-4,6-DNP	103	90	C ₁₃ H ₈ ClBrN ₂ O ₄ S	7.80	7.96	6.92	6.96	28	23
16.	3-Chloro-2-methyl-4,6-DNP	97	95	C ₁₃ H ₈ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₄ S	8.53	8.91	7.75	7.77	40	38

TABLE 2—CHLOROPHENYL-HALOGENONITROPHENYL-SULPHONES

Srl. No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. Formula	%Sulphur		%Nitrogen		%germination at 10 ppm.	
					Found	Req.	Found	Req.	AT	AN
1.	2,4-DNP	116	90	C ₁₂ H ₇ ClN ₂ O ₆ S	9.15	9.35	8.10	8.18	22	18
2.	2,6-DNP	138	75	C ₁₂ H ₇ ClN ₂ O ₆ S	9.42	9.35	8.12	8.18	15	20
3.	2,4,6-TNP	123	80	C ₁₂ H ₆ ClN ₃ O ₈ S	8.91	9.01	10.82	10.85	12	8
4.	2-Bromo-4,6-DNP	90	90	C ₁₂ H ₆ ClBrN ₂ O ₆ S	7.50	7.64	6.72	6.66	12	10
5.	3-Chloro-4,6-DNP	175	70	C ₁₂ H ₆ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₆ S	8.32	8.49	7.65	7.42	35	45
6.	4-Chloro-2,6-DNP	121	85	C ₁₂ H ₆ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₆ S	8.59	8.49	7.32	7.42	20	16
7.	4-methyl-2,6-DNP	183	74	C ₁₃ H ₉ ClN ₂ O ₆ S	8.85	9.00	7.83	7.90	25	22
8.	2,3-dichloro-4,6-DNP	128	72	C ₁₂ H ₅ Cl ₃ N ₂ O ₆ S	7.32	7.42	6.35	6.81	20	18
9.	2-Chloro-3-Bromo-4,6-DNP	130	80	C ₁₂ H ₅ Cl ₂ BrN ₂ O ₆ S	7.15	7.03	6.02	6.15	22	24
10.	2-Chloro-5-methyl-4,6-DNP	185	85	C ₁₃ H ₈ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₆ S	8.00	8.18	7.00	7.14	20	22
11.	2-Bromo-5-methyl-4,6-DNP	155	80	C ₁₃ H ₈ ClBrN ₂ O ₆ S	7.32	7.37	6.37	6.59	23	25
12.	3-Chloro-2-methyl-4,6-DNP	142	73	C ₁₃ H ₈ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₆ S	8.05	8.18	7.25	7.14	38	41

Note :- DNP and TNP refer to dinitro and trinitrophenyl respectively. AT and AN refer to *Alternaria tenuis* and *Aspergillus niger*. All melting points are uncorrected.

Fungicidal Activity: For fungicidal assay the method of Montgomery and Moore³ was used as test fungi.

The results of antifungal activity have been studied. It was observed that the presence of electronegative group at ortho and/or para position to sulphide and sulphone linkage enhances the toxicity. Nitrophenyl sulphones were found to be more active than the corresponding sulphides. Thus nitrogroup and halogen atom at ortho and para position in both the classes of compounds enhanced fungitoxicity. However, a chlorine atom at meta position decreased it. The presence of methyl group was found to decrease the fungitoxicity.

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Volumetric Estimation of Fluorine

TARUN KUMAR GHOSH

Inorganic Chemistry Laboratory, University College of Science, Calcutta

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FLUORINE is usually estimated gravimetrically as calcium fluoride or as lead chlorofluoride. The common volumetric procedures¹ involve distillation of fluorine as fluosilicic acid. The method involves complicated operations and requires time. The present method is simple and quicker.

Fluoride ion forms with beryllium a very stable fluoberyllate² ion in solution at a $pH < 8$. Barium fluoberyllate, like barium sulphate, is sparingly soluble and has a solubility³ of 1.5×10^{-3} gmequiv/litre at 25°. In the present method fluorine as fluoride ion is first converted to fluoberyllate⁴ by addition of beryllium ion in solution and then quantitatively precipitated as barium fluoberyllate and the barium estimated with EDTA. The corresponding amount of fluorine in barium fluoberyllate can be easily calculated. The method can also be used for the estimation of fluorine in rocks and materials.

Experimental

Reagents: Sodium fluoride solution standardised by calcium fluoride method.

Beryllium chloride solution	2% in water.
Barium chloride solution	5% in water.
Zinc chloride solution	0.01M
Eriochrome Black T	.1%
EDTA	0.01M

All reagents were of A. R. Grade.

Apparatus: Polythene apparatus were used when working with fluoride solution.

Procedure: Sodium fluoride solution containing 10 mg to 85 mg of fluorine was taken in a 250 ml beaker and beryllium chloride solution was added in excess. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 3–4 with *N*/100 hydrochloric acid using methyl orange as indicator. The solution was heated to 50°–60° and barium chloride solution was added drop wise with constant stirring till precipitation was complete. The precipitate was digested for an hour on a hot asbestos board. The precipitate was filtered, washed with hot water till free from chloride and finally transferred to the same beaker with a jet of water. 25 ml of 0.1M EDTA was now added to the precipitate and stirred to dissolution. 5 ml of ammonium chloride buffer was added, warmed and the excess EDTA back titrated with standard zinc chloride solution using Eriochrome black T as indicator, colour changes from pink to blue indicated end point. Results are given in Table I.

TABLE 1

Fluoride taken in mg.	Fluoride found in mg.
10.6	11.00
21.2	21.6
31.8	31.5
42.4	42.8
53.0	53.6
74.2	75.0
84.8	85.1

Procedure for Rocks and Minerals: 200 mg of the sample was taken in a platinum crucible and fused with 3–4 times its weight of sodium carbonate with a pinch of sodium peroxide. The fused mass was taken up with water in a beaker and boiled to help dissolution. filtered and in the filtrate fluorine is estimated as in the general procedure. Results are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Sample No.	Fluorine %	
	Distillation method	Present method.
D 183	0.37	0.39
D 199	0.26	0.28
D 213	0.29	0.32
F/1	0.35	0.36

Results

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